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Exploring Services Rendered by Librarians with Open Source Library Management Software in North-central University Libraries, Nigeria

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Abstract

Keywords:

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Introduction: This study investigated the services rendered by librarians using Open Source Library Management Software (OSLMS) in university libraries in the North-Central zone of Nigeria.

Methodology: A descriptive research design was adopted, gathering data from 301 librarians across federal and state universities in the zone using a total enumeration sampling approach. The instrument used in this study was a questionnaire, and its reliability, assessed using Cronbach's alpha, yielded a satisfactory coefficient of 0.81. Data collected from the survey underwent analysis using descriptive statistics, including frequency counts, percentages, and mean values.

Findings: The findings revealed that the prominent OSLMS used in university libraries in North-Central Nigeria include KOHA, Evergreen, and NewGenLib, with KOHA being the most widely known and used. The majority of respondents agreed that the services provided by librarians using OSLMS in university libraries include web-based OPAC, advanced acquisition, a full catalogue system for library stock management, export and import records, ISO 2709, administration control, MARC 21 and UNIMARC for professional cataloguing and classification, Z39.50 protocol for cataloguing, circulation, management of the database of library users, web-based interface, Management Information System (MIS), and serials control.

Conclusion/Recommendations: The study suggested increasing publicity and promotion of various OSLMS to provide a wider choice of library automation systems in the region. Additionally, research on integrated library software in Nigeria's federal, state, and private universities should explore the adoption, functionality, and user satisfaction of OSLMS to enhance library service efficiency.

Introduction

Universities serve as focal points for learning and are environments where researchers, particularly at the faculty level, are expected to demonstrate high productivity. They play a crucial role in facilitating research endeavours both in Nigeria and worldwide. These institutions dedicate themselves to higher education and research, offering academic degrees in various fields at both undergraduate and postgraduate levels.

University libraries are crucial academic units in higher education, providing diverse information to support teaching, learning, and research objectives. They acquire, process, organise, and disseminate information across various fields of knowledge. As technology advances, library operations are evolving from traditional to modern, with open source library management software being a key factor in this transformation. They serve as hubs for learning activities and information dissemination (Omeluzor et al., 2017; Godwin, 2021).

Randhawa (2013) defines open source library management software (OSLMS) as computer software that is made available under a licence or arrangement, such as the public domain, which allows users to examine, modify, enhance, and distribute the software in its original or modified form. Open source library management software refers to software that allows users the freedom to execute, duplicate,

disseminate, examine, modify, exchange, and enhance it for various purposes (Randhawa, 2013; Ango & Ogbomo, 2024). According to Randhawa (2018), open source library software offers libraries the advantage of avoiding the upfront expenses associated with commercial software while also providing them with more autonomy over their operational environment.

The use of library automation systems was a preserve of wealthier libraries, mainly those in developed countries that could afford proprietary library automation systems (Bwalya, 2021). This, however, has changed due to the omnipresence of open source library management systems (OSLMS) such as Koha, Evergreen, ABCD, NewGenLib and OpenBiblio. With the increase in the use of OSLMS in university libraries in Nigeria, librarians and library staff expectation are centred on usefulness and usable integrated library management software. While usefulness deals with the feature necessary to carry out library task, usability describes how easy it is for library staff to accomplish library functions using OSLMS. The availability of open source library management software has given impetus to libraries, especially in developing countries such as Nigeria, to automate their operations in order to bring about efficiency and improved service delivery (Bwalya, 2021). Thus, Karadia (2016) highlighted that librarians use OSLMS Modules/services for Acquisition; Cataloguing; OPAC

(Online Public Access Catalogue); Circulation; and Serial Control.

Statement of the Problem

The study focuses on Open Source Library Management Software (OSLMS), which offers librarians the capability to automate various library tasks. OSLMS enhances data accuracy, streamlines procedures, reduces costs, and empowers library staff. Despite these advantages, university libraries in Nigeria, particularly in the North-central region, predominantly rely on manual operations (Uzomba, Oyebola, & Izuchukwu, 2015). The services rendered by librarians using OSLMS include administration, cataloguing and metadata management, circulation management, acquisition and collection development, Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC), serials management, digital resource management, reporting and analytics, Interlibrary Loan (ILL) services, patron management, and customisation and user support (Bwalya, 2021). To address this issue, this study investigates the services rendered by librarians with OSLMS in North-Central University Libraries, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

i. What are the types of open-source library management software used by

librarians in North-central university libraries, Nigeria?

ii. What are the services rendered with open-source library management software by librarians in the North-central university libraries, Nigeria?

Literature Review

Types of Open-source Library Management Software used in Libraries

The software mostly used in libraries today is Integrated Library Software (ILS). The ILS is a multipurpose software application that enable libraries catalogue, manage, and circulate the library materials to users. There exist various open-source ILS software which are been employed in several Nigerian university libraries. Examples include Koha, NewGenLib, Evergreen and Openbiblio (Moruf, Sani, & Abu, 2020). Otieno (2016) opined that Open-source software is an application or a computer program that is made freely available for the public, the source code can be modified and distributed. Its license warrants a user to access the source codes and programming language used in the compilation of the software. This allows libraries irrespective of their size or type to tailor the software to meet their specific need. Leeladharan and Ilammaran (2015) noted that the tools of Open-source Software (OSS) and its implementation in libraries improves access to diverse information sources and by that means provides a cost-effective and dynamic

service to a larger extent of clients within a shorter period.

Despite the fact that Open-source software is widely used, especially by western countries, the adoption of OSS is negated by the misconceptions of developing countries (Rafiq & Ameen, 2009, as cited in Leeladharan & Ilammaran, 2015). Even in developed countries, certain individuals who are heads of Information Technology (IT) divisions of top-level organisations also reject the usage of OSS for different reasons. While some are of the opinion that OSS is irrelevant to their business, others believed OSS to be unreliable due to absence of ongoing support, a few of them even mentioned that another reason was that lack of time to adopt OSS (Goode, 2005, as cited in Leeladharan & Ilammaran, 2015). However, on a positive note, librarians, managers and IT staff believe that organisations could discover that their capabilities have increased and their set goals and objectives can be met when they make use of OSS with the minimal allocated organisation's budget and IT staffing (Hedgebeth, 2007, as cited in Leeladharan & Ilammaran, 2015). Based on their unique needs and goals, libraries select various types of open-source software. Here is a list of open-source software options that librarians can employ for tasks such as information dissemination, storage, and retrieval within libraries:

Koha: Koha is the first comprehensive integrated library management system ever developed. It supports numerous languages, including English, Chinese, French, Arabic, and more (Reddy & Kumar, 2013; Bwalya, 2021; Ango & Ogbomo, 2024). It is suitable for managing library systems of different sizes and types. Koha runs on a browser and uses the interface of OPAC. The software is freeware and users are able to modify the software to meet their library needs. The development of Koha is sponsored by volunteers, support companies and libraries of varying types and sizes globally. It gets strength from its enthusiastic users, businesses, and libraries that develop it. The program works on Web, Servers, and Linux.

Tella, Dina, Olaniyi, Memudu, and Oguntayo (2017) posted that Koha is primarily designed to be user-oriented and librarian-friendly. The software features a simple and clear interface that is easy for both librarians and patrons to navigate. Koha offers a variety of Web 2.0 functionalities, including tagging, commenting, social sharing, and RSS feeds. It also provides a range of other features. Koha supports union catalogue capabilities and offers customisable and straightforward search options. Managing circulation and transactions is made easy, and its acquisitions system accurately handles budgets and pricing information, including supplier and currency conversion. There is also a simplified

acquisitions system available for smaller libraries. Koha can efficiently manage any number of branches, patrons, patron categories, item categories, items, currencies, and other fields. The software includes an easy-to-use serials system for managing magazines or newspaper clippings. Additionally, it offers comprehensive reporting facilities, the ability to create reading lists for members, and accurate management of statistics for each field. An overdue management facility is also included, making Koha a robust and versatile library management system (Tella, Dina, Olaniyi, Memudu, & Oguntayo, 2017; Bwalya, 2021; Ango & Ogbomo, 2024).

Evergreen: Evergreen is a library management system developed by the Georgia Public Library Service (GPLS) to support libraries in the Public Information Network for Electronic Services (PINES) consortium. It was developed in 2004 and successfully migrated to PINES in 2006 (Riewe, 2008; Bwalya, 2021; Ango & Ogbomo, 2024). Evergreen is a stable and mature OSLMS, with modules like acquisition, cataloguing, circulation, serials, and Web OPAC. Written in Perl, C, and JavaScript, it runs on an Apache server and uses the PostgreSQL database management system. It can be installed on Linux, Windows, and Mac operating systems and conforms to industry standards like MARC and XML (Londhe & Patil, 2015). The program can work with Mac, Web, and Linux. Evergreen is particularly

known for its scalability and reliability, which makes it suitable for large library consortia and networks. It offers powerful cataloguing, search, and reporting capabilities, and its open architecture allows for extensive customisation (Bwalya, 2021).

NewGenlib (NGL): NewGenLib is an open-source ILS developed in India in 2005 by the Kesavan Institute of Information and Knowledge Management and Verus Solutions Pvt. Ltd. It gained a significant user base (Kurmar & Thomas, 2009; Bwalya, 2021). The system includes modules for acquisitions, technical processing, serials management, administration, MIS reports, task scheduling, and OPAC. Written in Java, it runs on the Apache Tomcat server and uses PostgreSQL database management. It conforms to industry standards like MARC, XML, Dublin Core MODS 3.0, and AGRIS (Muruli & Kumar, 2014). For federated searching, NewGenLib uses Z39.50 and is OAI-PMH compatible.

OpenBiblio: OpenBiblio is a free library management system developed by Dave Stevens in 2002 and now maintained by Hans van der Weij in the Netherlands (Bwalya, 2017). It is written in Preprocessor Hypertext Language (PHP) and available in multiple languages, including English, French, Spanish, and Russian. OpenBiblio's latest release, version 0.7.2, was released in August 2014. It includes modules such as Web OPAC,

circulation, cataloging, administration, and reports. The system runs on Apache servers and uses a MySQL database management system. It complies with industry standards like MARC and ISO but does not support the Z39.50 protocol (Bwalya, 2021).

PMB: The PMB, initially called PhpMyBiblio, is an open-source library management system developed and maintained by the French company PMP Services (Londhe & Patil, 2015). With over 13 years of existence, PMB is available in multiple languages and is written in PHP. It offers four essential features: library management, watch and documentary products, editorial content publication, and electronic document management. PMB's modules are divided into two: the management module, which includes specific functions for librarians, and the OPAC module, which is a highly customisable portal. PMB conforms to all library and information science industry protocols and standards, allowing the use of the Z39.50 protocol for searching, retrieving, and importing bibliographic records from other library management systems (Bwalya, 2017). It also supports keeping bibliographic records in UNIMARC, ISO 2709 record exchange formats, and XML data formats. PMB is also compatible with the Open Archive Initiative (OAI) server and client, allowing bibliographic records to be harvested by search engines and other harvesters (Smile, 2017, as cited in Bwalya, 2017).

Services Rendered to Users in the Library using Library Management Software

Chigwada (2018) explained that open source integrated library software services are used by librarians to automate housekeeping tasks in libraries. These modules include administration, cataloguing, circulations, serial acquisitions, reports, and online public access catalogues (Oyovwe-Tinuoye & Omosekejim, 2022). The library management system's backbone is the administration module. It is used to configure a library system, such as by creating passwords for staff and establishing loan periods. Cataloguing is the mirror of the library that reveals the collection within a specific library (Reddy, 2013; Chigwada, 2018). Dhamdhare (2016) stressed the administrative module of OSLMS allows specifying user's profiles and assigning users to them to define access to any subset of different modules and their databases. In as much as the administrative module of OSLMS is important, the circulation module is another important feature of OSLMS. Chattopadhyay and Makhopadhyay (2016) emphasised the significance of circulation modules by characterising them as a series of specific, repetitive, and systematic operations that form an essential part of library functioning. OSLMS must support effective circulation. To do this effectively, it requires at least an initial database to work effectively. This database comprises

information regarding borrowers, such as personal details and membership status; documents borrowed; bibliographic data used; availability; as well as circulation systems that manage loan rules such as issue and return dates. An effective library management system includes a circulation system that facilitates member registration, user status maintenance, and title availability monitoring, as well as fine collection from members (Omopupa, Adedeji & Suluman-Haroon, 2019; Chukwueke, 2022). This ensures efficient operations that meet user needs effectively.

The cataloguing module contains bibliographic frameworks that are applicable to original cataloguing and, in particular, copy cataloguing (Chukwueke, 2022; Oyovwe-Tinuoye & Omosekejim, 2022). A good cataloguing programme should lead to a well-structured record in the OPAC. The OPAC in the OSS allows users to search for items and access online services. The module's basic functionality includes the capability for users to search for and view information about any item. OPAC features include patron login, book suggestions, book reserves or holds, and similar services. If these modules do not work, library software usage will decrease (Chukwueke, 2022).

Hussaini et al. (2017) pointed out that the usage of software management software/databases cannot be applied in all the sections of the library, in view of this, the authors asserted that some of the

sections in the library where software/databases can be applied and be used to render services to users in the library. These sections encompass acquisition, circulation, circulation, OPAC, serial control, and administration, and management. Integration library software plays a central role in providing circulation services, facilitating online charging and discharging of information resources, as well as patron registration and related services. OPAC serves both library staff and patrons by directing them towards processed information resources within their library system. Users can input search terms such as title, author name, class mark, or call number to locate materials quickly and efficiently. A majority of libraries now rely on OPAC systems as automated library service platforms that cover an extensive array of library services. Cataloguing services are also provided through integrated library software that adheres to standardised cataloguing codes, importing MARC-formatted data directly into the OPAC of different libraries; this process involves retrieving information from online catalogues of institutions such as the Library of Congress and other participating libraries (Omopupa, Adedeji & Sulyman-Haroon, 2019; Chukwueke, 2022)..

The module for acquisition is used to order, receive, and invoice library materials in print or non-print. The module allows for easy and efficient tracking of library expenditures. The library can

purchase items on behalf of its users (Omopupa, Adedeji & Sulyman-Haroon, 2019; Oyovwe-Tinuoye & Omosekejim, 2022). Vendor codes, names, and addresses are part of the information in the acquisition module (Reddy & Kumar, 2013; Chigwada, 2018). The reports module allows you to generate a number of reports using the library management software, such as fines and overdue items. Karadia (2016) highlighted open-source library management software modules Acquisition, Cataloguing, OPAC, Circulation, Serial Control Management, or Report System Maintenance Facilities or Parameters.

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive research design, specifically adopting a descriptive survey design, for its capacity to gather data that can be generalised to a larger population. The research population consisted of 301 librarians from both federal and state universities in North-Central Nigeria. The study employed a total enumeration sampling approach. The instrument for the study was a self-developed questionnaire. The questionnaire consists of three sections. Section A focuses on respondents demographic variables; Section B is on the various open source library management software used by librarians. This section has ten items on a dichotomous scale of

Agree (A) and Disagree (D). Section C is on the services, open source library management software is used for. This section has twenty items presented on a four (4) point scale with Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2, Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1. The information was put on a weighted scale with numerical values attached to it in the questionnaire as follows: 4 = SA, 3 = A, 2 = SD, 1 = D, and 4 = VH, 3 = H, 2 = L, and 1 = VL. The instrument's reliability, assessed using Cronbach's Alpha, yielded a satisfactory coefficient of 0.81. The researcher distributed copies of the questionnaire to the respondents with the help of research assistants to speed up the process of data collection. Data collected from the survey underwent analysis using descriptive statistics, encompassing frequency counts, percentages, and mean values. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23 was employed for this analysis, with a criterion mean score below 2.50 considered negative and a score above 2.5 considered positive. Some of the OSLMS in today's market include BiblioQ, Emilda, Librarian, OpenBiblio, EspaBiblio, CodeAchi, Evergreen, Gnuteca, Invenio, InfoCID, Jayuya, Koha, NewGenLib. OPALS, OpenAmapthèque, PhpMyLibrary, PMB, Senayan etc. (Omopupa, Adedeji & Sulyman-Haroon, 2019; Oyovwe-Tinuoye & Omosekejim, 2022).

Results

Table 1: Questionnaire Response

Number of Questionnaire Administered	Number of Questionnaire Returned	Percentage of Questionnaire Returned
301	290	96%

A total of 301 copies of the questionnaire were distributed, out of which 290 (96%) were returned, resulting in a response rate of 96%. With a response rate of 96%, which is well over the acceptable threshold

of 60% for most studies, the study is considered to have a satisfactory response rate (Dulle et al., 2010, as cited in Ango & Ogbomo, 2024).

Table 2: Academic Qualification of the Respondents

Academic Qualification	Frequency	Percentage (%)
B.Sc./B.LS/B.Tech/BLIS	64	22.1
M.Sc./M.LS/M.Tech	196	67.6
PhD	30	10.3
Total	290	100.0

From Table 2, it shows that the M. Sc./M.LS/M. Tech holders have the highest frequency of 196(67.6%), and those with B. Sc./B.LS/B. Tech were 64(22.1%), and the Ph.D. holders were 30(10.3%). It implies that most librarians hold an M. Sc./M.LS/M. Tech degree.

Table 3: Designation of the Respondents

Designation	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Assistant Librarian	64	22.0
Librarian II	47	16.2
Librarian I	71	24.5
Senior Librarian	42	14.5
Principal Librarian	40	13.8
Deputy University Librarian	15	5.2
University Librarian	11	3.8
Total	290	100.0

Table 3 above, shows the responses of the respondents on designation of the librarians. There are 71 (24.5%) Librarian I, 64 (22.1%) Assistant Librarian, 47 (16.2%) Librarian II, 42 (14.5%) Senior

Librarian, 40(13.8%) Principal Librarian, 15(5.2%) Deputy University Librarian and 11 (3.8%) University Librarians. This implies that majority of the librarians are Librarian I.

Research Question 1: What are the types of open-source library management software used by librarians in North-central university libraries, Nigeria?

Table 4: Open source library management software used by librarians.

OSLMS	Agree		Disagree		Total	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
KOHA	260	89.6	30	10.4	290	100
Evergreen	10	3.5	280	96.5	290	100
OPALS	0	0	0	0	0	0
Openbiblio	0	0	0	0	0	0
Invenio	0	0	0	0	0	0
PMB	0	0	0	0	0	0
NewGenLib	20	6.9	270	93.1	290	100
CodeAchi	0	0	0	0	0	0
Librarian	0	0	0	0	0	0
BiblioQ	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 4 shows that 260 (89.6%), agreed that the type of open source software library management their university adopted is KOHA, 20 (6.9%) respondents agreed they use NewGenLib, and 10 (3.5%) respondents agreed they adopted and use Evergreen as the type of OSLMS adopted in their university libraries for their daily routine. It can be concluded that the types of open source library

management software used by librarians in university libraries in North-Central Nigeria are KOHA, NewGenLib and Evergreen.

Research Question 2: What are the services rendered with open-source library management software by librarians in the North-central university libraries, Nigeria?

Table 5: Services rendered with open source library management software.

The services to which OSLMS is used	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean
Web based Online Public Access Catalogue	206	78	4	2	3.68
MARC 21 and UNIMARC for professional cataloguing and classification	181	96	9	4	3.57
Z39.50 protocol for cataloguing	179	101	6	4	3.57
Multilingual and multi-user support	165	104	11	10	3.46
Circulation i.e. Patrons registration, borrowing and returning of library books, etc.	177	106	1	6	3.57
Web based interface	169	114	3	4	3.54
Advanced Acquisition and full Catalogue system for library stock management	176	108	3	3	3.58
Barcode	157	122	5	6	3.48
Reports	160	118	8	4	3.50
Reservation facility of library books	142	125	11	12	3.37
Management of database of library users	170	113	4	3	3.55
RSS feed	168	74	23	25	3.33
Export and import records, ISO 2709	176	108	3	3	3.58
Management of Serials	107	151	18	14	3.21
Administration control	182	99	4	5	3.58
Management Information System (MIS) i.e. usage statistics	185	85	13	7	3.54
Inter Library Loan (ILL)	166	84	18	22	3.36
Outreach Services	127	95	42	26	3.11
Digital Media Archiving	161	79	29	21	3.31
Serials Control	160	99	13	18	3.38
Aggregate Mean					3.46
Criterion Mean					2.50

Table 5 revealed that with an aggregate mean of 3.46 which is greater than the criterion mean of 2.50, it can be concluded that the librarians strongly agreed that the services to which open source library management software is used for in their university libraries are web-based OPAC, Advanced Acquisition, and a full catalogue system for library stock management, export and import records, ISO 2709, administration control, MARC 21 and UNIMARC for professional cataloguing and classification, Z39.50 protocol for cataloguing, circulation, i.e., Patron registration, borrowing and returning of library books, etc., management of the database of library users, Web-based interface, Management Information System (MIS), i.e., usage statistics, reports, barcodes, Multilingual and multi-user support, Serials Control, Reservation Facility of Library Books, Inter Library Loan (ILL), RSS Feed, Digital Media Archiving, Management of Serials, and Outreach Services.

Discussion of Findings

The findings revealed that the types of OSLMS used in university libraries in North-Central Nigeria are KOHA, Evergreen, and NewGenLib with the most widely known and used as KOHA. This is in accordance with Iroaganachi et al. (2015), who revealed that Koha software has gained popularity over the years, especially in academic libraries in Nigeria, where it is the most frequently used

software in South Africa and Nigeria. This finding backs up Moruf et al. (2020) research, on various open-source software that has been employed in several Nigerian university libraries, including Koha, NewGenLib, Evergreen, and Openbiblio. This signifies that there are three major open source library management softwares used in North-Central Nigeria by librarians in university libraries in order to ease the routines of libraries faster and more efficiently. This also collaborates with Okuonghae and Idubor (2020), and Uzomba et al. (2015) that most libraries now subscribe to the use of KOHA and NewGenLib in performing some key library routine functions because of the flexibility, functionalities and updating capability of the software. KOHA is widely used in many libraries in Africa because it is an open source and it has the capability to automate the key routine activities in the library.

The findings showed that the services librarians use for OSLMS in university libraries in North-Central Nigeria are web-based OPAC, advanced acquisition, and a catalogue system for stock management, cataloguing, and circulation. This is in line with the study of Oyovwe-Tinuoye and Omosekejimi (2022) who found that the user registration, charging and discharging of library materials, referral service, reference service, internet service, electronic library service, OPAC and book reservation routines in a library is high. This is in accordance with Chigwada

(2018) which explained that open source integrated library management software services are used to execute automated housekeeping activities in the library by the librarians for the administration, cataloguing, circulation, serials, acquisition, reports, online public access catalogue modules are available although with different capabilities. This implies that open source library management software are multifunction, adaptable software applications that allow libraries to acquire, process, manage, catalogue and circulate its materials to their patrons.

Conclusion

This study delved into the Exploring services rendered by librarians with OSLMS in North-central university libraries, Nigeria. The findings revealed that the types of OSLMS used in university libraries in North-Central Nigeria are KOHA, Evergreen, and NewGenLib with the most widely used as KOHA. These results indicated that the services rendered by librarians with OSLMS in university libraries in North-Central Nigeria include web-based OPAC, advanced acquisition, and a catalogue system for stock management, cataloguing, and circulation. The study highlights the importance of enhancing and exploring services rendered by librarians with OSLMS in North-central university libraries, Nigeria to improve the utilisation of open-source library management software.

Recommendations

In view of the following, the study recommended the following;

1. The study revealed that Koha is the most widely known and used Open Source Library Management System (OSLMS) for library automation in North-Central Nigeria. Other OSLMS options, such as OPALS, OpenBiblio, ABCD, Evergreen, NewGenLib, PMB, and LIBRARIAN, are less known, primarily due to a lack of publicity. This lack of awareness limits the choices for library automation systems in the region, suggesting a need for increased promotion and awareness of these alternatives.
2. Further research should be conducted on integrated library software in federal, state, and private university libraries in Nigeria. This research should explore the adoption, functionality, and user satisfaction of OSLMS. By identifying gaps and opportunities for improvement, this research can enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of library services rendered by librarians, ultimately benefiting the academic community in North-central Nigeria.

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